

Questions to Anfacó

Interview with David Alonso and Martín Rodríguez

Anfacó is responsible for the demonstration and validation of BIORECER methodology. What improvements does it bring to the bio-based products industry? How well is it being received by stakeholders? What achievements would you highlight?

The BIORECER methodology brings significant improvements to the bio-based resources industry by standardising the certification of origin through traceability of these raw materials, ensuring their sustainability and quality. Thanks to this, it enables:

- Greater trust in the value chain by validating compliance with circular economy criteria and environmental footprint.
- Visibility of these by-products in the market, facilitating access to sustainable raw materials.
- Alignment with European regulations, promoting more competitive and circular markets.

Regarding stakeholder acceptance, the methodology is being well received, especially by companies seeking to differentiate themselves in terms of sustainability. The active participation of key players (raw material producers, processing industry, etc.) in the various case studies where we are testing this new methodology reflects a strong interest in adopting this new framework.

The main achievements so far are:

- Development of a new certification system.
- Successful validation in different value chains across the European continent.
- Creation of a strong collaborative network between companies and sectors.

What competitive advantages does using this methodology offer for bio-based product companies?

There are several advantages that companies adopting this methodology will gain, especially in a market increasingly focused on sustainability:

- The BIORECER certification acts as a seal of environmental quality and circularity, attracting customers and partners committed to these kinds of standards who currently require such criteria from their suppliers.
- Access to new markets: Companies that adopt this methodology will be able to give visibility to their by-products through direct contact with other companies via the BIORECER platform, leading to commercial agreements.
- Reduction of regulatory risks by ensuring the traceability and sustainable origin of raw materials.
- Economic efficiency: Cost optimisation by valorising by-products that were previously discarded, generating new sources of income.
- Attraction of investment by aligning with certain benefits from European funds, and the possibility of obtaining financing through calls designed within this framework.

How will the end consumer perceive the certification of these by-products through BIORECER?

The consumer is an increasingly decisive figure who demands well-informed decisions, valuing transparent and easily understandable information about the environmental impact of products. BIORECER can generate a positive perception regarding these current needs, as it offers a sustainability guarantee through its own seal, certifying the traceability of by-products and fostering trust in the use of raw materials backed by recognised certification systems.